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Review Paper

Endocrine and Molecular Mechanisms Linking Thyroid Dysfunction to Male and Female Infertility

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ABSTRACT

Infertility is a major global health concern, affecting around 8–12% of couples, with male factors contributing to nearly half of all cases. Thyroid dysfunction has emerged as a significant yet often overlooked contributor to infertility in both men and women. Thyroid hormones play a crucial role in regulating reproductive physiology through their interaction with the hypothalamic–pituitary–gonadal axis, influencing ovulation, menstrual cycles, spermatogenesis, and hormone balance. This review examines the relationship between thyroid disorders—hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism, and autoimmune thyroid disease—and reproductive dysfunction. In females, hypothyroidism leads to hormonal imbalances, anovulation, menstrual irregularities, and reduced ovarian reserve, while hyperthyroidism disrupts cycle regularity and ovulation. Autoimmune thyroid disease further contributes to infertility and increased miscarriage risk, even in euthyroid individuals. In males, thyroid dysfunction adversely affects spermatogenesis, resulting in reduced sperm count, motility, morphology, and increased oxidative stress. Additionally, oxidative stress is identified as a key mechanism linking thyroid dysfunction to impaired reproductive outcomes. Clinical evidence also highlights the impact of untreated thyroid disorders on pregnancy outcomes, including miscarriage, preterm delivery, and fetal developmental complications. Importantly, many of these effects are reversible with appropriate thyroid management. Overall, early diagnosis and timely treatment of thyroid abnormalities are essential to improve fertility outcomes and reproductive health in both sexes.

INTRODUCTION

Infertility is a significant global reproductive health concern, affecting approximately 8–12% of

couples, with male factors contributing to nearly 50% of cases overall^[2]. Increasing evidence highlights the strong association between infertility and endocrine disorders, among which

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thyroid dysfunction is one of the most common and clinically relevant abnormalities in both women and men.^[1,3]

Thyroid hormones play a crucial role in regulating reproductive physiology through their interaction with the hypothalamic–pituitary–ovarian (HPO) axis in females and the hypothalamic–pituitary–gonadal (HPG) axis in males. They influence key processes such as menstrual cyclicity, follicular development, ovulation, endometrial receptivity, spermatogenesis, and steroidogenesis.^[6,3] Thyroid dysfunction—both hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism—can disrupt these processes, leading to impaired fertility outcomes in both sexes. The burden of thyroid abnormalities among infertile individuals is considerable. In women, thyroid dysfunction is reported in 15–25% of infertile cases in Asian populations, with prevalence in India ranging from 20–26%, predominantly hypothyroidism.^[3,4,8] Autoimmune thyroid disease, particularly Hashimoto's thyroiditis, is also common and has been associated with unexplained infertility, recurrent pregnancy loss, and reduced success rates of assisted reproductive technologies.^[2,8,33] In men, thyroid dysfunction has been linked to alterations in semen parameters, including reduced sperm concentration, motility, and abnormal morphology [1], with prevalence among men with sexual dysfunction ranging from 3.4% to 57.1%^{4]}. Emerging evidence suggests that oxidative stress may serve as a key unifying mechanism linking thyroid dysfunction and infertility. Thyroid hormone imbalance disrupts cellular metabolism and mitochondrial function, leading to excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which adversely affect oocyte quality, spermatogenesis, embryo development, and endometrial receptivity.^[5,6] This review aims to synthesize current evidence on thyroid dysfunction and infertility, focusing on its epidemiology, clinical impact, and therapeutic

implications. It emphasizes the importance of early diagnosis and appropriate management of thyroid disorders to improve reproductive outcomes in both females and males.

Physiology of Thyroid Hormones and Their Role in Reproduction

Hypothalamic–Pituitary–Thyroid Axis: Basic Physiology

The hypothalamic–pituitary–thyroid (HPT) axis is a multi-level regulatory system responsible for maintaining metabolic homeostasis and energy balance. The axis begins at the hypothalamus, which secretes thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH) in response to metabolic and energy-sensing signals such as leptin, neuropeptide Y, and agouti-related peptide.⁹ TRH stimulates thyrotropic cells in the anterior pituitary gland to release thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH). TSH then acts on the thyroid gland to stimulate the synthesis and secretion of the thyroid hormones triiodothyronine (T3) and tetraiodothyronine (T4).¹⁰ Once released into circulation, T3 and T4 are transported bound to plasma proteins, mainly thyroxine-binding globulin, transthyretin, and albumin. Although T4 is produced in larger quantities by the thyroid gland, it is considered a prohormone and must be converted into the biologically active hormone T3 within peripheral tissues. This conversion occurs through the action of deiodinase enzymes type 1 and type 2.¹¹ (figure 1) Alternatively, T4 may be converted into reverse T3, an inactive metabolite, by deiodinase type 3. This peripheral conversion provides fine regulation of thyroid hormone action and prevents excessive T3 activity.¹¹ At the cellular level, thyroid hormones enter target cells through specific transporters such as monocarboxylate transporter 8 and monocarboxylate transporter 10, or by passive diffusion. Inside the cell, T3 binds to thyroid hormone receptors located in the nucleus. These receptors form a heterodimer with the

retinoid X receptor and regulate gene transcription by interacting with coactivator proteins. In the absence of T3, the thyroid hormone receptor–retinoid X receptor complex binds to corepressor proteins, suppressing gene transcription. T3 and T4 also exert negative feedback control at the hypothalamic and pituitary levels, inhibiting further release of TRH and TSH, thereby maintaining hormonal balance.¹²

Thyroid Hormones and Female Reproductive Physiology

Interaction Between the Thyroid Axis and the Hypothalamic–Pituitary–Gonadal Axis

Reproductive function is regulated by the hypothalamic–pituitary–gonadal (HPG) axis, which integrates signals related to energy balance, stress, and homeostasis. The central reproductive system receives input from metabolic signals such as glucose, insulin, insulin-like growth factor-1, and leptin; stress-related mediators such as glucocorticoids and corticotropin-releasing hormone; and thyroid hormones.¹³

Many of these signals are processed by kisspeptin–neurokinin B–dynorphin neurons, which play a critical role in initiating reproductive hormone secretion. These neurons release kisspeptin, which stimulates pulsatile secretion of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) from hypothalamic neurons. GnRH then triggers the release of luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) from the anterior pituitary. LH and FSH act on the theca and granulosa cells of the ovary to regulate folliculogenesis and the synthesis of sex steroids and peptides.¹³ Thyroid hormones and related hormones such as TRH, TSH, T3, and T4 exert facilitatory and modulatory effects at multiple levels of the HPG axis.¹²

Role of Thyrotropin-Releasing Hormone in Reproduction

Thyrotropin-releasing hormone primarily regulates the HPT axis but also indirectly influences reproductive function.¹⁴ In primary hypothyroidism, increased TRH secretion leads to elevated prolactin levels because TRH is a potent stimulator of prolactin release.¹⁵ Prolactin plays an essential role in mammary gland development and lactation, but elevated prolactin levels inhibit reproductive function.¹⁶ Prolactin suppresses hypothalamic GnRH secretion both directly and indirectly. It reduces the expression of kisspeptin messenger RNA, leading to decreased GnRH release.¹⁷ Additionally, increased prolactin stimulates dopamine secretion, which further inhibits GnRH release and alters kisspeptin signaling.¹⁸

Prolactin and dopamine also reduce pituitary responsiveness to GnRH.¹⁹ Furthermore, prolactin can stimulate progesterone secretion from the corpus luteum, potentially prolonging its lifespan and contributing to menstrual irregularities observed in hypothyroidism.²⁰

Role of Thyroid-Stimulating Hormone in Reproduction

Thyroid-stimulating hormone is a glycoprotein hormone that shares a common alpha subunit with luteinizing hormone and follicle-stimulating hormone. Elevated TSH levels have been implicated in precocious puberty, particularly in Van Wyk–Grumbach syndrome, due to cross-reactivity with follicle-stimulating hormone receptors.²¹

TSH receptors are expressed in ovarian follicular cells, Leydig cells, and endometrial tissue, indicating a direct role for TSH in reproductive tissues.²² TSH has also been shown to promote endometrial proliferation, particularly in women with endometriosis.²³ Additionally, TSH interacts closely with leptin, a hormone secreted by adipocytes that signals energy sufficiency to the reproductive axis. TSH promotes adipocyte

proliferation and leptin secretion, thereby indirectly influencing kisspeptin neurons. In hypothyroid states, elevated TSH levels are associated with increased leptin levels, which normalize following levothyroxine therapy. Conversely, leptin also regulates TSH secretion by influencing TRH production in the hypothalamus, highlighting a bidirectional relationship between TSH and leptin in reproductive regulation.²⁴

Role of Triiodothyronine and Tetraiodothyronine in Reproductive Regulation

The precise mechanisms by which triiodothyronine and tetraiodothyronine regulate gonadotropin secretion are not fully understood. However, animal studies have demonstrated that thyroid hormone administration increases the expression of kisspeptin and gonadotropin-releasing hormone genes, whereas hypothyroid states reduce kisspeptin expression.²⁵

Thyroid hormones may exert their reproductive effects indirectly through interactions with other regulatory systems, including gonadotropin-inhibiting hormone, insulin, glucocorticoids, and neuropeptide Y.²⁶ Thyroid hormone receptors have been identified on kisspeptin–neurokinin B–dynorphin neurons in several mammalian species, suggesting a direct regulatory role.²⁵

Thyroid hormones also influence metabolic pathways that affect reproductive function. They enhance hypothalamic insulin signaling, which promotes GnRH secretion by suppressing neuropeptide Y, an inhibitory regulator of GnRH neurons. Hypothyroid states impair insulin secretion and signaling, further contributing to reproductive dysfunction.^{26,27}

Stress-related pathways also interact with thyroid hormones. Glucocorticoids suppress thyroid hormone production and conversion, while thyroid hormones influence glucocorticoid receptor expression and responsiveness.²⁸ Additionally,

thyroid hormone-mediated increases in estradiol levels enhance luteinizing hormone feedback mechanisms, indicating complex interactions between thyroid hormones, stress hormones, and sex steroids.²⁹

Recent evidence suggests that gonadotropin-inhibiting hormone, also known as RFamide-related peptide-3 in humans, may serve as an additional pathway through which thyroid hormones regulate reproductive function. Hypothyroidism has been shown to increase gonadotropin-inhibiting hormone expression and delay puberty in animal models, effects that are reversed when this pathway is disrupted. Given the presence of gonadotropin-inhibiting hormone in the human hypothalamus, a similar mechanism may contribute to reproductive dysfunction in hypothyroid individuals.³⁰⁻³²

PATHOLOGY -

1. HYPOTHYROIDISM IN FEMALE REPRODUCTION

1. Neuroendocrine Dysregulation of the Hypothalamic–Pituitary–Ovarian Axis :

Hypothyroidism results in reduced circulating T3 and T4 levels, leading to loss of negative feedback at the hypothalamic–pituitary axis. This causes increased secretion of thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH) and thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH).⁶ Elevated TRH also stimulates prolactin release, resulting in hyperprolactinemia. Increased prolactin suppresses pulsatile gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) secretion. Consequently, luteinizing hormone (LH) pulsatility is disrupted and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) dynamics are altered. Although LH and FSH levels may remain within normal limits, their abnormal secretion impairs follicular maturation and ovulation. This leads to anovulatory cycles, luteal phase defects, menstrual

irregularities, and infertility in hypothyroid women.³³

Table no 1: Evidence Supporting Neuroendocrine Disruption in Hypothyroidism

Study (Author, Year)	Study Design / Population	Age / Subjects	Key Results & Comments
Goswami et al. (2009). ³⁴	Cross-sectional case-control	160 infertile women vs 80 fertile controls, reproductive age	Positive correlation between TSH and prolactin; infertile group had <i>higher</i> hyperprolactinemia (41% vs 15%) and more menstrual disorders (mainly oligomenorrhea). Hypothyroid infertile women had significantly higher prolactin vs euthyroid/controls. Supports TRH-driven hyperprolactinemia. ³⁴
Sharma et al. (2023). ³⁵	Hospital-based descriptive study	150 infertile women	TSH positively correlated with prolactin and negatively with LH & FSH (p <0.05). Suggests thyroid dysfunction alters gonadotropins in infertility. ³⁵
Acharya et al. (2011). ³⁶	Observational cohort	80 hypothyroid women	FSH & LH levels were significantly lower in both subclinical and overt hypothyroid women; menstrual dysfunction dominated by oligomenorrhea. Supports impaired gonadotropin secretion. ³⁶

2 Ovarian and Peripheral Hormonal Effects of Thyroid Hormone Deficiency:

Thyroid hormone receptors are present in ovarian granulosa cells and oocytes, indicating a direct role in follicular development. Under normal conditions, thyroid hormones enhance granulosa cell responsiveness to FSH and support estradiol production.⁶ In hypothyroidism, reduced thyroid hormone signaling decreases follicular sensitivity to gonadotropins, leading to impaired follicle maturation, poor steroidogenesis, and reduced oocyte quality. Clinically, this may present as diminished ovarian reserve, reflected by reduced

antral follicle count and elevated early follicular phase FSH levels.³³

Additionally, hypothyroidism alters peripheral sex steroid metabolism. Reduced thyroid hormone levels decrease hepatic production of sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG), lowering total circulating estrogen and androgen levels. Altered androgen metabolism and increased peripheral aromatization further disturb estrogen balance. This hormonal imbalance contributes to endometrial dysfunction and a high prevalence of menstrual abnormalities, including oligomenorrhea, amenorrhea, anovulatory bleeding, and menorrhagia.³⁷

Table 2: Evidence Supporting Ovarian and Peripheral Hormonal Effects of Thyroid Hormone Deficiency

Author (Year)	Type of Study	No. of Population/ Age of Subjects	Results and comments
Rao M et al., 2020. ⁴	Retrospective clinical study	2,568 infertile women. reproductive age (289 with SCH; subgroup ≥ 35 years)	Subclinical hypothyroidism was associated with lower AMH, reduced antral follicle count, and elevated early follicular phase FSH, indicating diminished ovarian reserve and reduced follicular responsiveness to gonadotropins. ⁴
Saran S et al., 2016. ³⁸	Observational clinical study	30 reproductive-age hypothyroid women (with euthyroid controls)	Overt hypothyroidism was associated with reduced serum estradiol and testosterone levels, which normalized after thyroxine therapy, confirming altered peripheral sex-steroid metabolism in hypothyroid states. ³⁸
Ruth KS et al., 2020. ³⁹	Mendelian Randomization study using genome-wide association data (GWAS-based)	>180,000 women of European ancestry from UK Biobank; adult women (40–69 years)	Genetically predicted higher TSH levels were associated with lower SHBG levels and altered circulating sex hormone concentrations. This supports a causal relationship between thyroid function and hepatic SHBG production, explaining altered sex-steroid profiles seen in hypothyroid states. ³⁹

3. Impact on Fertility, Pregnancy, and Fetal Development

Hypothyroidism impairs female fertility by causing anovulation, luteal phase defects, poor oocyte quality, and reduced endometrial receptivity. Elevated TSH levels are more frequently observed in women with unexplained infertility. During early pregnancy, fetal development depends entirely on maternal thyroid hormone supply.⁴⁰ Overt hypothyroidism

increases the risk of miscarriage, preeclampsia, placental abruption, preterm delivery, postpartum hemorrhage, low birth weight, and stillbirth. In inadequately treated cases, fetal loss rates may reach 60%. Thyroid hormones are essential for fetal brain development, regulating neuronal migration, myelination, and synapse formation. Maternal hypothyroidism, especially in the first trimester, can lead to long-term neurodevelopmental impairment in offspring.⁴¹

Table 3: Evidence Supporting Impact of Maternal Hypothyroidism on Fertility, Pregnancy Outcomes, and Fetal Neurodevelopment

Author (Year)	Type of Study	No. of Population & Age	Results and Comments
Poppe K et al., 2002. ³³	Prospective cohort study	438 infertile women; reproductive age	Women with elevated TSH or thyroid autoimmunity had significantly lower pregnancy rates after assisted reproduction compared with euthyroid women, demonstrating that thyroid dysfunction impairs fertility and reduces conception success. ³³
Allan WC et al., 2000. ⁴²	Prospective population-based cohort study	9,403 pregnant women; reproductive age	Maternal overt and subclinical hypothyroidism were associated with increased risks of miscarriage, preterm delivery, and other obstetric complications, confirming adverse pregnancy outcomes linked to elevated TSH. ⁴²
Haddow JE et al., 1999. ⁴¹	Prospective cohort study	62 children born to hypothyroid mothers compared with 124 controls; mothers of reproductive age	Children of untreated hypothyroid mothers during pregnancy had significantly lower IQ scores (≈ 7 points lower on average), confirming that early maternal thyroid hormone deficiency impairs fetal neurodevelopment. ⁴¹

2. HYPERTHYROIDISM IN FEMALE REPRODUCTION

1. Neuroendocrine Dysregulation of the Hypothalamic–Pituitary–Ovarian Axis:

Hyperthyroidism, often caused by Graves' disease, toxic multinodular goiter, or thyroid nodules, leads to excessive T3 and T4 and suppressed TSH. In Graves' disease, autoantibodies overstimulate the thyroid,

disrupting hypothalamic–pituitary feedback.⁶ This alters GnRH, LH, and FSH secretion, causing menstrual irregularities, most commonly oligomenorrhea and amenorrhea, and ovulatory dysfunction. Metabolic and adrenergic effects of thyroid excess further impair reproductive hormone coordination. Overall, hyperthyroidism dysregulates the endocrine network, negatively affecting reproductive hormone rhythms and contr

Table 4: Evidence Supporting Central (HPO Axis) Dysregulation in Hyperthyroidism and Its Impact on Fertility contributing to subfertility and cycle disturbances.⁴³

Study & Year	Design & Population	Key Findings	Interpretation
Zähringer et al., 2000.⁴⁴	Experimental clinical study; 14 untreated Graves' patients (7F/7M) vs 12 healthy controls; women sampled in early follicular phase	LH secretion was significantly elevated in hyperthyroid patients, while FSH rose only in men; pulsatility of gonadotropins remained largely normal	Indicates that hyperthyroidism increases gonadotropin output but does not completely disrupt HPO rhythms, supporting central dysregulation of reproductive hormones without total loss of pulsatile control. ⁴⁴
Quintino Moro et al., 2014.⁴⁵	Cross-sectional observational; 193 women with Graves' disease, ages 18–50	52% of women met criteria for infertility (>12 months unprotected intercourse); younger women (<35) were particularly affected	Provides strong clinical evidence linking hyperthyroid autoimmune disease with reproductive dysfunction and subfertility, reinforcing the real-world consequences of HPO dysregulation. ⁴⁵
Potiris et al., 2024 (Review).⁴⁶	Narrative review summarizing multiple studies	Oligomenorrhea and amenorrhea are the most frequent menstrual disturbances in hyperthyroid women; menorrhagia is less common	Supports the notion that thyroid excess primarily affects cycle regularity and ovulation rather than inducing heavy bleeding, aligning with central and ovarian mechanism changes. ⁴⁶

2. Ovarian and Peripheral Hormonal Effects of Thyroid Hormone Excess:

Excess thyroid hormones affect ovarian and peripheral reproductive physiology both directly and indirectly. Thyroid hormone receptors in ovarian tissue increase metabolic activity in granulosa cells and oocytes, altering follicular growth.⁴⁷ Peripherally, hyperthyroidism raises sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG), increasing

total estrogen and testosterone but often reducing free active fractions. It also enhances peripheral conversion of androgens to estrogens. These changes disrupt the estrogen–progesterone balance, impairing follicular development, luteal function, and endometrial stability, leading to irregular cycles, hypomenorrhea, ovulatory dysfunction, and reduced fertility.⁴⁸

Table 5: Evidence for Ovarian and Peripheral Hormonal Effects of Thyroid Hormone Excess

Study & Year	Design & Population	Key Findings	Interpretation
Poppe K et al., 2007.³³	Clinical observational and review; women with hyperthyroidism	SHBG significantly higher in hyperthyroid patients compared to controls; free estradiol decreased in many	Provides clinical evidence for peripheral disruption of steroid activity. Shows how excess thyroid hormone indirectly reduces ovarian tissue exposure to active sex steroids, contributing to impaired follicular development. ³³
Krassas GE et al., 2010.⁶	Cross-sectional study; 30 hyperthyroid women, ages 20–40	40% had shortened menstrual cycles; 30% showed ovulatory dysfunction	Provides direct clinical correlation between hyperthyroidism and ovarian/peripheral reproductive changes. Reinforces that both central and peripheral effects contribute to fertility issues. ⁶

3. Impact on Fertility, Pregnancy, and Fetal Development:

Hyperthyroidism can impair fertility by causing irregular ovulation and altered luteal phase support, although evidence is less consistent than for hypothyroidism. During pregnancy, uncontrolled hyperthyroidism increases the risk of miscarriage, preterm delivery, preeclampsia, and maternal cardiac complications.⁴⁰ In Graves'

disease, thyroid-stimulating antibodies (TRAb) can cross the placenta, potentially causing fetal or neonatal thyrotoxicosis, which may result in tachycardia, intrauterine growth restriction, hydrops fetalis, or stillbirth if untreated. Effective maternal thyroid control improves outcomes, but antithyroid therapy must be carefully managed to balance maternal euthyroidism with fetal safety.⁴³

Table 6: Evidence Linking Maternal Hyperthyroidism to Adverse Pregnancy and Fetal Outcomes

Study & Year	Design & Population	Key Findings	Interpretation
Casey BM et al., 2006.⁴⁹	Prospective cohort; 129 pregnant women with hyperthyroidism vs 258 controls	Overt hyperthyroidism associated with higher rates of miscarriage, preterm birth, and preeclampsia	This study clearly links maternal thyrotoxicosis to adverse pregnancy outcomes. It highlights the importance of timely diagnosis and management to reduce maternal and fetal complications. ⁴⁹

<p>Nguyen L et al., 2017.⁵⁰</p>	<p>Retrospective cohort; 200 pregnancies in women with Graves' disease</p>	<p>TRAbs detected in maternal serum correlated with fetal tachycardia, growth restriction, and neonatal thyrotoxicosis</p>	<p>Provides evidence for the immune-mediated mechanism of fetal thyroid stimulation. It underlines the need for monitoring maternal TRAbs to anticipate and prevent fetal complications.⁵⁰</p>
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➤ **AUTO-IMMUNE THYROID DISEASE :**

1. Neuroendocrine Dysregulation of the Hypothalamic–Pituitary–Ovarian Axis

Autoimmune thyroid disease (AITD) is characterized by thyroid peroxidase (TPOAb) and thyroglobulin antibodies (TgAb) and is common in reproductive-age women. Reproductive impairment may occur even in euthyroid women, indicating immune-mediated effects beyond hormone deficiency.³³ Thyroid autoimmunity alters hypothalamic–pituitary–ovarian (HPO) axis regulation. Subtle changes in GnRH pulsatility disturb LH and FSH secretion patterns. This disrupts coordinated follicular development and ovulation.⁵¹ AITD frequently coexists with subclinical hypothyroidism due to reduced thyroid reserve. During pregnancy or increased thyroid demand, this impaired adaptive capacity worsens endocrine balance. Overall, immune dysregulation contributes to reproductive dysfunction independent of overt hypothyroidism.⁵³

2. Ovarian and Peripheral Hormonal Effects

AITD is associated with reduced ovarian reserve even when thyroid hormone levels are normal. Women with positive thyroid autoantibodies show lower anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) levels.³³ A reduced antral follicle count indicates compromised follicular quantity. Immune-mediated mechanisms, including inflammatory cytokines, may impair follicular quality.

Autoimmune cross-reactivity may directly affect ovarian tissue.⁵² Thyroid autoimmunity can disturb the follicular microenvironment. Subtle alterations in estrogen–progesterone signaling may occur. These changes impair endometrial receptivity and luteal phase adequacy, reducing implantation potential.⁵⁴

3. Impact on Fertility, Assisted Reproductive Technology, and Pregnancy

Women with AITD have a higher risk of infertility and early pregnancy loss, even if euthyroid. The increased miscarriage risk is strongly linked to thyroid autoantibody positivity.⁵¹ In assisted reproductive technology (IVF/ICSI), miscarriage rates are higher in antibody-positive women. Effects on implantation and clinical pregnancy rates are less consistent.⁵² Levothyroxine does not uniformly improve ART outcomes in euthyroid women. However, it may reduce miscarriage risk when subclinical hypothyroidism is present. During pregnancy, AITD is associated with miscarriage, preterm delivery, and placental dysfunction. Some studies suggest possible adverse neuro-developmental outcomes in offspring.^[54]

Table 7: Clinical Implications of Differential Thyroid Dysfunction on Female Fertility

PATHOPHYSIOLOGICAL ASPECT	HYPOTHYROIDISM	HYPERTHYROIDISM	AUTOIMMUNE THYROID DISEASE (AITD)
Neuroendocrine Dysregulation of the Hypothalamic–Pituitary–Ovarian Axis	↓ T3/T4 → ↑ TRH → ↑ TSH and hyperprolactinemia prolactin suppresses GnRH pulsatility → altered LH/FSH secretion → anovulation and luteal phase defects	↑ T3/T4 → suppressed TRH and TSH; altered GnRH, LH, and FSH secretion due to excess thyroid hormone action and increased adrenergic tone → irregular ovulation	Presence of TPOAb/TgAb causes immune-mediated disruption of HPO axis; subtle GnRH and gonadotropin alterations can occur even in euthyroid state; high risk of progression to subclinical hypothyroidism
Ovarian and Peripheral Hormonal Effects	Reduced thyroid hormone signaling in granulosa cells → ↓ follicular sensitivity to FSH, poor follicle maturation, ↓ estradiol; ↓ SHBG → altered estrogen–androgen balance; ↑ peripheral aromatization	Excess thyroid hormone action accelerates ovarian metabolism; ↑ SHBG → ↑ total but ↓ free sex steroids; disturbed estrogen–progesterone balance; hypomenorrhea common	Immune-mediated reduction in ovarian reserve (↓ AMH, ↓ AFC); inflammatory follicular microenvironment; subtle steroidogenic imbalance impairing endometrial receptivity
Impact on Fertility, Pregnancy, and Fetal Development	Markedly reduced fertility; ↑ unexplained infertility; pregnancy risks include miscarriage, preeclampsia, placental abruption, preterm birth, stillbirth; impaired fetal neurodevelopment if untreated	Mild–moderate fertility impairment; pregnancy complications include miscarriage, preeclampsia, preterm birth, heart failure; TRAb-mediated fetal/neonatal thyrotoxicosis in Graves’ disease	↑ infertility and miscarriage risk even when euthyroid; higher miscarriage rates after IVF/ICSI; levothyroxine benefits mainly when subclinical hypothyroidism coexists; ↑ obstetric complications

Spermatogenesis.

Spermatogenesis is a highly regulated biological process governed by the coordinated activity of the hypothalamic–pituitary–gonadal (HPG) axis. The initiation of this axis begins at the level of the hypothalamus, which integrates multiple internal and external signals to regulate male reproductive function. Neural inputs related to circadian rhythm, nutritional status, stress, and sexual maturation converge on specialized hypothalamic

neurons. During puberty and adulthood, these neurons acquire sensitivity to metabolic and neuroendocrine cues, resulting in the pulsatile release of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH). This pulsatility is critical, as continuous GnRH secretion leads to down regulation of pituitary gonadotropin release.

GnRH is transported via the hypophyseal portal circulation to the anterior pituitary gland, where it binds to GnRH receptors on gonadotroph cells. This interaction stimulates the synthesis and

episodic secretion of two key gonadotropins: luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH). The frequency and amplitude of GnRH pulses influence the relative secretion of these hormones, thereby fine-tuning testicular function.

LH primarily targets the Leydig cells located in the interstitial tissue of the testes. Upon LH stimulation, Leydig cells synthesize and secrete testosterone, the principal androgen responsible for male reproductive development. Testosterone diffuses locally into the seminiferous tubules and also enters systemic circulation. Within the tubules, testosterone plays a crucial paracrine role in supporting germ cell development.

FSH acts on Sertoli cells, which line the seminiferous tubules and provide structural and metabolic support to developing germ cells. Under FSH stimulation, Sertoli cells produce androgen-binding protein (ABP), which binds testosterone and maintains a high intratubular androgen concentration. Sertoli cells also form the blood–testis barrier, secrete growth factors, and regulate the microenvironment required for germ cell maturation. Additionally, they release inhibin B, which provides negative feedback to the pituitary to regulate FSH secretion.

The combined action of testosterone and Sertoli cell support creates an optimal intratubular environment for spermatogenesis. Within the seminiferous tubules, spermatogonia undergo mitotic proliferation, followed by meiotic division to form haploid spermatids. These spermatids then undergo spermiogenesis, a differentiation process that results in the formation of mature spermatozoa. Thus, spermatogenesis represents the final outcome of precise neuroendocrine signaling initiated at the hypothalamic level and executed within the seminiferous tubules.

Role of thyroid hormones on spermatogenesis genomically and non-genomically: GENOMICALLY

Thyroid hormones, principally 3,5,3'-triiodothyronine (T3) and thyroxine (T4), play an important regulatory role in testicular development and function through both genomic and non-genomic mechanisms^[7]. Among these, genomic actions represent a key pathway through which thyroid hormones influence spermatogenesis and testicular cell maturation.

Genomic effects are primarily mediated by T3, the biologically active form of thyroid hormone, which enters target cells and binds to thyroid hormone receptors (TRs) located within the nucleus of Sertoli and Leydig cells^[58,59]. Upon binding, the T3–TR complex interacts with specific DNA sequences known as thyroid hormone response elements (TREs), leading to activation or repression of target gene transcription and subsequent protein synthesis^[59]. Through this mechanism, thyroid hormones exert long-term effects on cellular growth, differentiation, and functional activity within the testis.

Thyroid hormone receptors are encoded by two genes, TR α and TR β , which give rise to five receptor isoforms—TR α 1, TR α 2, TR α 3, TR β 1, and TR β 2—through alternative splicing. Among these, TR α 1, TR β 1, and TR β 2 are functional receptors capable of binding T3, whereas TR α 2 and TR α 3 lack a hormone-binding domain. These non-binding isoforms can still attach to TREs and act as dominant negative regulators by competing with T3-bound receptors, thereby suppressing thyroid hormone–dependent gene transcription^[6].

Within the testis, TR α 1 is the predominant receptor isoform expressed in germ cells, particularly from intermediate spermatogonia to pachytene spermatocytes, as well as in Sertoli

cells. Sertoli cell development and function are further modulated by TR β 1 and TR β 2, highlighting the importance of thyroid hormone signaling in shaping the seminiferous epithelium^[58]. Rather than acting directly on germ cells, T3 primarily influences spermatogenesis indirectly by regulating the proliferation, differentiation, and functional maturation of non-germ cells.

NON-GENOMICALLY:

In addition to their genomic actions, thyroid hormones exert rapid nongenomic effects that directly influence sperm function. These effects are mediated through binding to nonnuclear receptors located on the plasma membrane, cytoplasm, cytoskeleton, and mitochondria of spermatozoa. Activation of these extranuclear pathways triggers intracellular signaling cascades, particularly increased cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) production and calcium (Ca²⁺) mobilization, which together enhance flagellar activity and sperm motility^[7,60].

Thyroxine (T4) has been shown to rapidly stimulate sperm hyper-motility by increasing flagellar movement, resulting in improved recovery of motile sperm during swim-up procedures^[60]. In comparative observations, exposure to T4 enabled all treated sperm samples to reach the minimum motile sperm threshold required for intrauterine insemination, outperforming pentoxifylline, a phosphodiesterase inhibitor commonly used to increase cAMP levels^[7]. These findings suggest a potential role for thyroid hormones in improving sperm preparation outcomes in assisted reproductive techniques. Besides T3 and T4, other iodothyronines may also act through nongenomic mechanisms. Reverse

triiodothyronine (rT3) has been reported to interact with cytoskeletal elements, while diiodothyronine (T2) preferentially targets mitochondria^[61]. However, their specific effects on spermatozoa remain insufficiently studied and warrant further investigation.

Thyroid hormones also play an important role in maintaining the redox balance of the testis, which is essential for sperm viability and motility^[60]. The sperm mid piece is rich in glutathione peroxidase (GPx), a selenium-dependent enzyme that protects against oxidative stress and inhibits apoptosis^[62]. Selenium is a key micronutrient for thyroid hormone metabolism, as it is required for iodothyronines deiodinases that convert T4 to the active hormone T3. In selenium-deficient men, supplementation has been associated with improved sperm motility as well as better thyroid immune status^[63].

Additional antioxidant systems in the testis include superoxide dismutase, γ -glutamyl transferase, catalase, glutathione-S-transferase, cytochrome c, melatonin, vitamins C and E, and zinc^[7]. Thyroid hormones modulate these defenses by enhancing γ -glutamyl transferase and catalase expression while downregulating GPx and cytochrome c, thereby contributing to optimal sperm function^[64,65]

HYPERTHYROIDISM:

Hyperthyroidism is consistently associated with adverse effects on spermatogenesis and semen quality. Excess circulating thyroid hormones negatively influence germ cell development and sperm function, leading to reductions in sperm concentration, motility, and normal morphology, along with a decrease in semen volume. Histological and functional studies indicate that hyperthyroid states may delay spermatogenic

progression, often resulting in maturation arrest. Structural changes such as reduced seminiferous tubule diameter, absence of pachytene spermatocytes, impaired mitochondrial activity, and decreased lipid content within germ cells further contribute to compromised sperm development^[65].

Clinically, thyrotoxicosis is frequently associated with asthenozoospermia, affecting more than half of hyperthyroid men. Oligozoospermia and teratozoospermia are reported in approximately 40% of patients and are often accompanied by hypospermia^[66]. Together, these abnormalities result in a marked reduction in overall semen quality, characterized by decreased sperm density, motility, and morphological integrity.

Several clinical studies support these observations. Early work by Hudson and Edwards demonstrated reduced progressive sperm motility in 16 adult men with Graves' disease compared with euthyroid controls^[67]. Subsequent studies confirmed these findings, with Krassas and colleagues

motility in treatment or improve sperm concentration less consistently of semen normalizations. Beyond control levels of the FT4—have damage and T3 and T4 increase the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to oxidative stress, which adversely affects sperm chromatin integrity, mitochondrial function, and membrane stability^[69,72].

Recent investigations have highlighted the relevance of thyroid hormones within seminal plasma. Seminal FT4 levels have been detected at measurable concentrations, and in vitro studies have shown that incubation of semen with low, physiological concentrations of levothyroxine reduces sperm necrosis and lipid peroxidation while improving chromatin compactness. These findings suggest that an optimal balance of thyroid hormones within seminal plasma may be necessary for maintaining sperm bio functional integrity. Although these observations open new perspectives for clinical applications in idiopathic male infertility, further studies are required to define physiological reference ranges for seminal FT3 and FT4^[70,72].

What is well established is that treatment of hyperthyroidism, restoring euthyroid or high-normal FT4 levels, leads to improvement in semen quality, reinforcing the concept that thyroid hormone-related sperm dysfunction is largely reversible.

Hyperthyroidism

Asthenozoospermia
Oligozoospermia
Teratozoospermia

spermatogenic support. This reduction in Sertoli cell number and function contributes to defective spermatogenesis and is associated with a decrease in overall testicular volume^[55,77]. Collectively, these hormonal and cellular alterations explain the detrimental effects of hyperthyroidism on male fertility, despite elevated circulating androgen levels.^[55]

compromise acrosomal integrity and mitochondrial activity, both of which are essential for sperm motility, fertilization capacity, and energy production^[83]. Consistent with other reproductive alterations seen in hypothyroidism, improvements in sperm motility and functional parameters are commonly observed after restoration of normal thyroid hormone levels^[77,84].

Overall, these findings highlight that hypothyroidism exerts a multifaceted yet largely reversible impact on male fertility by disrupting testicular cell maturation, androgen production, and sperm quality.

Primary hypothyroidism

Reduced T3 and T4 levels

Study(Author, year)	Study design/ Population	Subjects
Trummer et al (2001) ^[85]	Prospective observational study	305 infertile with idiop infertility
Zhang et al. (2025) ^[86]	Retrospective cohort, fertility clinic	8478 undergoing fer consultation
Nikoobakht et al. (2012) ^[87]	Case-control, clinical study	24 hypothy men vs 66 no controls

↓Delayed Sertoli cell maturation
Leydig cell dysfunction

Impaired germ cell support
↓Androgen synthesis

↓hCG receptor expression

↓Leydig cell maturation

Disrupted spermatogenesis
↓Testosterone(total&free)

Abnormal sperm morphology
Reduced intratesticular androgen (Teratozoospermia)
support

↓Sperm count and motility

Acrosomal damage and mitochondrial dysfunction

Male infertility

Improvement after thyroid hormone replacement.

Study(Author, year)	Study design/ Population	Subjects	Key results & comments
Azizi et al. (2021) ^[88]	Cross-sectional, large clinical cohort	5401 men seeking infertility care	<p>impact, leading to anovulation, hormonal disturbances, poor oocyte quality, and adverse pregnancy outcomes. Hyperthyroidism, although comparatively less severe, still contributes to menstrual irregularities, ovulatory dysfunction, and impaired fertility. Autoimmune thyroid disease adds an additional layer of complexity by affecting fertility even in the absence of overt hormonal abnormalities.</p> <p>In males, both hypo- and hyperthyroid states significantly impair spermatogenesis through hormonal imbalance, oxidative stress, and cellular dysfunction, ultimately reducing semen quality. Notably, many of these reproductive impairments show improvement following restoration of euthyroidism, but SERP was associated with significantly thyroid-related infertility. sperm DNA fragmentation index (DFI), a marker linked to poor fertility outcomes.</p> <p>Therefore, routine screening for thyroid function in infertile individuals is strongly recommended. Early detection and appropriate management can significantly enhance fertility outcomes, improve pregnancy success rates, and reduce long-term complications for both parents.</p>
Krassas & Perros (2003) ^[89]	Narrative clinical review	Mixed clinical data	<p>Summarized clinical evidence that hyperthyroidism clearly impacts sperm motility and quality, often reversible with euthyroidism.</p> <p>Hypothyroidism effects are more subtle, but can alter steroid metabolism and spermatogenesis.</p>

Table. 8 Clinical evidence linking thyroid disorders to male infertility

CONCLUSION

Thyroid dysfunction plays a critical and multifaceted role in infertility by disrupting hormonal balance, reproductive physiology, and cellular processes in both males and females. Hypothyroidism has a more pronounced negative

REFERENCES

1. Unuane D, Velkeniers B. Impact of thyroid disease on fertility and assisted conception. *Best Pract Res Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2020; 34:101378.
2. Popa EC, Maghiar L, Maghiar TA, Brihan I, Georgescu LM, Toderas BA, Sachelarie L, Hurjui LL, Huniadi A. Hashimoto's thyroiditis and female infertility: a clinical and statistical investigation of endocrine and ovarian markers. *J Clin Med.* 2025;14:4770.
3. Cho MK. Thyroid dysfunction and subfertility. *Clin Exp Reprod Med.* 2015;42(4):131-135. doi:10.5653/cerm.2015.42.4.131
4. Rao M, Zeng Z, Zhou F, et al. Effect of hypothyroidism on female reproductive hormones and infertility. *Reprod Biol Endocrinol.* 2020;18:76.
5. Mazzilli R, Medenica S, Di Tommaso AM, et al. The role of thyroid function in female and male infertility: a narrative review. *J Endocrinol Invest.* 2023;46:15-26.
6. Krassas GE, Poppe K, Glinioer D. Thyroid function and human reproductive health. *Endocr Rev.* 2010;31(5):702-755.
7. La Vignera S, Vita R. Thyroid dysfunction and semen quality. *Int J Immunopathol Pharmacol.* 2018;32:1-5.
8. Habbu PP, Shaikh AK. Study of thyroid dysfunction in association with infertility. *Int J Biochem Res Rev.* 2016;11(2):1-6.
9. Nillni EA. Regulation of the hypothalamic thyrotropin releasing hormone (TRH) neuron by neuronal and peripheral inputs. *Front Neuroendocrinol.* 2010;31:134-156.
10. Braun D, Schweizer U. Thyroid hormone transport and transporters. *Vitam Horm.* 2018;106:19-44.
11. Köhrle J, Frädriich C. Deiodinases control local cellular and systemic thyroid hormone availability. *Free Radic Biol Med.* 2022;193(Pt 1):59-79.
12. Brent GA. Mechanisms of thyroid hormone action. *J Clin Invest.* 2012;122:3035-3043.
13. Navarro VM. Metabolic regulation of kisspeptin—The link between energy balance and reproduction. *Nat Rev Endocrinol.* 2020; 16:407-420.
14. Sharma LK, Sharma N, Gadpayle AK, Dutta D. Prevalence and predictors of hyperprolactinemia in subclinical hypothyroidism. *Eur J Intern Med.* 2016;35:106-110.
15. Tashjian AH Jr, Barowsky NJ, Jensen DK. Thyrotropin releasing hormone: direct evidence for stimulation of prolactin production by pituitary cells in culture. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.* 1971;43:516-523.
16. Onishi T, Miyai K, Kumahara Y. Serum prolactin response to thyrotropin-releasing hormone in normal subjects and in patients with thyroid diseases. *Nihon Naibunpi Gakkai Zasshi.* 1975; 51:161-165.
17. Liu X, Herbison AE. Dopamine regulation of gonadotropin-releasing hormone neuron excitability in male and female mice. *Endocrinology.* 2013; 154:340-350.
18. Goodman RL, Maltby MJ, Millar RP, et al. Evidence that dopamine acts via kisspeptin to hold GnRH pulse frequency in check in anoestrous ewes. *Endocrinology.* 2012; 153:5918-5927.
19. Dairaghi L, Constantin S, Oh A, Shostak D, Wray S. The dopamine D4 receptor regulates gonadotropin-releasing hormone neuron excitability in male mice. *eNeuro.* 2022;9:ENEURO.0461-21.
20. Hapon MB, Motta AB, Ezquer M, Bonafede M, Jahn GA. Hypothyroidism prolongs corpus luteum function in the pregnant rat. *Reproduction.* 2007;133:197-205.

21. Anasti JN, Flack MR, Froehlich J, Nelson LM, Nisula BC. A potential novel mechanism for precocious puberty in juvenile hypothyroidism. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 1995; 80:276-279.
22. Dhole B, Gupta S, Shekhar S, Kumar A. A novel antigonadotropic role of thyroid stimulating hormone on Leydig cell-derived mouse Leydig tumor cells-1 line. *Ann Natl Acad Med Sci (India).* 2020; 56:30-37.
23. Agard JA, Duffy DM, Jacot T, Archer DF. Thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) receptor on granulosa cells. *Fertil Steril.* 2011;96: S118.
24. Seoane LM, Carro E, Tovar S, Casanueva FF, Dieguez C. Regulation of in vivo TSH secretion by leptin. *Regul Pept.* 2000; 92:25-29.
25. Henson JR, Carter SN, Freeman DA. Exogenous T3 elicits long day-like alterations in testis size and the RFamides kisspeptin and gonadotropin-inhibitory hormone in short-day Siberian hamsters. *J Biol Rhythms.* 2013; 28:193-200.
26. Salvi R, Castillo E, Voirol MJ, et al. Gonadotropin-releasing hormone-expressing neurons immortalized conditionally are activated by insulin: implication of the mitogen-activated protein kinase pathway. *Endocrinology.* 2006; 147:816-826.
27. Maejima Y, Kohno D, Iwasaki Y, Yada T. Insulin suppresses ghrelin-induced calcium signalling in neuropeptide Y neurons of the hypothalamic arcuate nucleus. *Aging (Albany NY).* 2011; 3:1092-1097.
28. Kiyohara M, Son YL, Tsutsui K. Involvement of gonadotropin-inhibitory hormone in pubertal disorders induced by thyroid status. *Sci Rep.* 2017; 7:1042.
29. Kumar A, Dewan R, Suri J, et al. Abolition of endocrine dimorphism in hyperthyroid males? An argument for the positive feedback effect of hyperoestrogenaemia on LH secretion. *Andrologia.* 2012; 44:217-225.
30. Gojska NM, Belsham DD. Glucocorticoid receptor-mediated regulation of Rfrp (GnIH) and Gpr147 (GnIH-R) synthesis in immortalized hypothalamic neurons. *Mol Cell Endocrinol.* 2014; 384:23-31.
31. Kirby ED, Geraghty AC, Ubuka T, Bentley GE, Kaufer D. Stress increases putative gonadotropin inhibitory hormone and decreases luteinizing hormone in male rats. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2009; 106:11324-11329.
32. Poling MC, Quennell JH, Anderson GM, Kauffman AS. Kisspeptin neurones do not directly signal to RFRP-3 neurones but RFRP-3 may directly modulate a subset of hypothalamic kisspeptin cells in mice. *J Neuroendocrinol.* 2013; 25:876-886.
33. Poppe K, Velkeniers B. Thyroid disorders in infertile women. *Ann Endocrinol (Paris).* 2003;64(1):45-50.
34. Goswami B, Patel S, Chatterjee M, Koner BC, Saxena A. Correlation of prolactin and thyroid hormone concentration with menstrual patterns in infertile women. *J Reprod Infertil.* 2009;10(3):207-212.
35. Sharma S, Meena KL, Tabiyad A, et al. Correlation between prolactin, thyroid hormones, luteinizing hormone, follicle-stimulating hormone, estradiol and progesterone in infertile women. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol.* 2023;12(2):389-395. doi:10.18203/2320-1770.ijrcog20230245
36. Acharya N, Mishra A, Mohanty S. Effect of hypothyroidism on female reproductive hormones. *Int J Clin Biochem Res.* 2011;26(3):227-231.
37. Longcope C, et al. The effect of thyroid dysfunction on sex hormone metabolism. *Thyroid.* 1998;8(10):909-913.

38. Saran S, Gupta BS, Philip R, Singh KS, Bende SA, Agroiya P. Effect of hypothyroidism on female reproductive hormones. *Indian J Endocrinol Metab.* 2016;20(1):108-113. doi:10.4103/2230-8210.172245
39. Ruth KS, Day FR, Tyrrell J, et al. Using human genetics to understand the disease impacts of thyroid function. *Nat Commun.* 2020; 11:576. doi:10.1038/s41467-020-14457-6
40. Alexander EK, Pearce EN, Brent GA, et al. 2017 guidelines of the American Thyroid Association for the diagnosis and management of thyroid disease during pregnancy and the postpartum. *Thyroid.* 2017;27(3):315-389. doi:10.1089/thy.2016.0457
41. Haddow JE, Palomaki GE, Allan WC, et al. Maternal thyroid deficiency during pregnancy and subsequent neuropsychological development of the child. *N Engl J Med.* 1999;341(8):549-555.
42. Allan WC, Haddow JE, Palomaki GE, et al. Maternal thyroid deficiency and pregnancy complications: implications for population screening. *J Med Screen.* 2000;7(3):127-130.
43. De Leo S, Lee SY, Braverman LE. Hyperthyroidism. *Lancet.* 2016;388(10047):906-918. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(16)00278-6
44. Zähringer S, Tomova A, von Werder K, Keller E, Pfeiffer EF. The influence of hyperthyroidism on the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis. *Exp Clin Endocrinol Diabetes.* 2000;108(6):372-376.
45. Quintino-Moro A, Zantut-Wittmann DE, Tambascia M, Vaisman M. High prevalence of infertility among women with Graves' disease. *Int J Endocrinol.* 2014; 2014:982705.
46. Potiris G, Pappa T, Valsamakis G. Thyroid disorders and female fertility: a review. *Hellenic J Obstet Gynecol.* 2024;23(1):12-22.
47. Silva JF, Ocarino NM, Serakides R. Thyroid hormones and female reproduction. *Biol Reprod.* 2018;99(5):907-921.
48. Mansourian AR. Female reproduction physiology adversely manipulated by thyroid disorders: a review of literature. *Pak J Biol Sci.* 2013; 16:112-120.
49. Casey BM, Dashe JS, Wells CE, et al. Hyperthyroidism in pregnancy: maternal and neonatal outcomes. *Obstet Gynecol.* 2006;107(2 Pt 1):337-345.
50. Nguyen L, Laurberg P, Andersen SL, et al. Maternal thyroid-stimulating antibodies and fetal outcomes in Graves' disease pregnancies. *Thyroid.* 2017;27(11):1347-1355.
51. Negro R, Stagnaro-Green A. Diagnosis and management of subclinical hypothyroidism in pregnancy. *BMJ.* 2014;349:g4929.
52. Toulis KA, Goulis DG, Venetis CA, et al. Thyroid autoimmunity and infertility: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Hum Reprod Update.* 2010;16(6):643-652.
53. Korevaar TIM, Medici M, Visser TJ, Peeters RP. Thyroid disease in pregnancy: new insights in diagnosis and clinical management. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol.* 2017;5(1):65-75.
54. Busnelli A, Somigliana E, Benaglia L, et al. Thyroid autoimmunity and IVF outcomes: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Hum Reprod Update.* 2016;22(6):775-790.
55. Borght MV, Wyns C. Fertility and infertility: Definition and epidemiology. *Clin Biochem.* 2018;62:2-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinbiochem.2018.03.012>.
56. Babatunde EM, Emokpae MA. A comprehensive review of thyroid dysfunction: hidden player in male infertility. *Fertil Reprod.* 2024;6(4):166-175. doi:10.1142/S2661318224300046.

57. Gabrielson AT, Sartor RA, Hellstrom WJG. The impact of thyroid disease on sexual dysfunction in men and women. *Sex J Med Rev.*2019;7(1):57–70.
58. Wagner MS, Wajner SM and Maia AL (2008) The role of thyroid hormone in testicular development and function. *Journal of Endocrinology* 199(3): 351–365.
59. Jannini EA, Ulisse S and D’Armiento M (1995) Thyroid hormone and male gonadal function. *Endocrine Reviews* 16(4): 443–459.
60. Mendeluk GR and Rosales M (2016) Thyroxin is use-ful to improve sperm motility. *International Journal of Fertility & Sterility* 10(2): 208–214.
61. Davis PJ, Goglia F and Leonard JL (2016) Nongenomic actions of thyroid hormone. *Nature Reviews Endocrinology* 12(2): 111–121.
62. Duntas LH and Benvenga S (2015) Selenium: An element for life. *Endocrine* 48(3): 756–775.
63. Ahsan U, Kamran Z, Raza I, et al. (2014) Role of selenium in male reproduction: A review. *Animal Reproduction Science* 146(1–2): 55–62.
64. Choudhury S, Chainy GB and Mishro MM (2003) Experimentally induced hypo- and hyper-thyroidism influence on the antioxidant defence system in adult rat testis. *Andrologia* 35(3): 131–140
65. Romano RM, Gomes SN, Cardoso NC, et al. (2017) New insights for male infertility revealed by alterations in spermatic function and differential testicular expression of thyroid-related genes. *Endocrine* 55(2): 607–617.
66. Abalovich M, Levalle O, Hermes R, et al. (1999) Hypothalamic-pituitary-testicular axis and seminal parameters in hyperthyroid males. *Thyroid* 9(9): 857–863.
67. Hudson RW and Edwards AL (1992) Testicular function in hyperthyroidism. *Journal of Andrology* 13(2): 117–124.
68. Krassas GE, Pontikides N, Deligianni V, et al. (2002) A prospective controlled study of the impact of hyperthyroidism on reproductive function in males. *Journal of Clinical Endocrinology and Metabolism* 87(8): 3667–3671.
69. Dobrzyńska MM, Baumgartner A, Anderson D (2004) Antioxidants modulate thyroid hormone- and noradrenaline-induced DNA damage in human sperm. *Mutagenesis* 19:325–330.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/mutage/geh037>
70. Mintziori G, Kita M, Duntas L, Goulis DG (2016) Consequences of hyperthyroidism in male and female fertility: pathophysiology and current management. *J Endocrinol Invest* 39:849–853. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40618-016-0452-6>
71. Zamoner A, Barreto KP, Filho DW et al (2007) Hyperthyroidism in the developing rat testis is associated with oxidative stress and hyperphosphorylated vimentin accumulation. *Mol Cell Endocrinol* 267:116–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mce.2007.01.005>
72. De Groot L, Abalovich M, Alexander EK et al (2012) Management of thyroid dysfunction during pregnancy and postpartum: an endocrine society clinical practice guideline. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 97:2543–2565. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jc.2011-2803>
73. Ruder H, Corvol P, Mahoudeau JA et al (1971) Effects of induced hyperthyroidism on steroid metabolism in man. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 33:382–387. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jcem-33-3-382>
74. Rojdmarm S, Berg A, Kallner G (1988) Hypothalamic-pituitary-testicular axis in patients with hyperthyroidism. *HormRes*

- 29:185–190.
<https://doi.org/10.1159/000181000>
75. Vermeulen A, Verdonck L, Van Der Straeten M, Orié N (1969) Capacity of the testosterone-binding globulin in human plasma and influence of specific binding of testosterone on its metabolic clearance rate. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 29:1470–1480. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jcem-29-11-1470>
76. Velázquez EM, Arata GB (1997) Effects of thyroid status on pituitary gonadotropin and testicular reserve in men. *Arch Androl* 38:85–92. <https://doi.org/10.3109/01485019708988535>
77. Rajender S, Monica MG, Walter L, Agarwal A (2011) Thyroid, spermatogenesis, and male infertility. *Front Biosci Elit* E3:843–855 <https://doi.org/10.2741/e292>
78. Palmero S, De Marchis M, Gallo G, Fugassa E (1989) Thyroid hormone affects the development of Sertoli cell function in the rat. *J Endocrinol* 123:105–111. <https://doi.org/10.1677/joe.0.1230105>
79. Patel N, Kashanian JA (2016) Thyroid dysfunction and male reproductive physiology. *Semin Reprod Med* 34:356–360. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0036-1593491>
80. Hess RA, Cooke PS, Bunick D, Kirby JD (1993) Adult testicular enlargement induced by neonatal hypothyroidism is accompanied by increased Sertoli and germ cell numbers. *Endocrinology* 132:2607–2613. <https://doi.org/10.1210/endo.132.6.8504761>
81. Hardy MP, Kirby JD, Hess RA, Cooke PS (1993) Leydig cells increase their numbers but decline in steroidogenic function in the adult rat after neonatal hypothyroidism. *Endocrinology* 132:2417–2420. <https://doi.org/10.1210/endo.132.6.8504746>
82. Krassas GE, Papadopoulou F, Tziomalos K et al (2008) Hypothyroidism has an adverse effect on human spermatogenesis: a prospective, controlled study. *Thyroid* 18:1255–1259. <https://doi.org/10.1089/thy.2008.0257>
83. Romano RM, Gomes SN, Cardoso NCS et al (2017) New insights for male infertility revealed by alterations in spermatid function and differential testicular expression of thyroid related genes. *Endocrine* 55:607–617. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12020-016-0952-3>
84. Trokoudes KM, Skordis N, Picolos MK (2006) Infertility and thyroid disorders. *Curr Opin Obstet Gynecol* 18:446–451. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.gco.0000233941.89919.31>
85. Trummer H, Ramschak-Schwarzer S, Haas J, Habermann H, Pummer K. Thyroid hormones and thyroid antibodies in infertile males. *Fertil Steril.* 2001;76(2):254-257. doi:10.1016/S0015-0282(01)01875-1.
86. Zhang Y, Xiao X, Liu Y, et al. Associations between thyroid hormones and sperm parameters in men undergoing fertility consultation. *Andrology.* 2025;[Epub ahead of print]. doi:10.1111/andr.70110.
87. Nikoobakht MR, Aloosh M, Nikoobakht N, Mehryar A, Biniiaz F, Karjalian MA. The role of hypothyroidism in male infertility and erectile dysfunction. *Urol J.* 2012;9(1):405-409.
88. Azizi F, Amouzegar A, Mehran L, Delshad H, Tohidi M, et al. Thyroid autoimmunity and male infertility: results from a population-based cohort (Tehran Thyroid Study). *BMC Endocr Disord.* 2021;21:214. doi:10.1186/s12902-021-00773-y.
89. Krassas GE, Perros P. Thyroid disease and male reproductive function. *J Endocrinol Invest.* 2003;26(4):372-380.

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